

A review on Artificial Intelligence-based evaluation of written production

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Abstract:

This literature review examines the integration and impact of Automatic Essay Scoring (AES) and Automatic Writing Evaluation (AWE) systems in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. For this purpose, empirical studies published between January 2020 and December 2024 in high-impact databases were analyzed. Conventional AWE systems, exemplified by tools such as Grammarly and Pigai, were found to improve grammatical accuracy; however, their limited feedback scope restricts improvements in coherence, organization, and originality. Innovative approaches that combine AWE with peer assessment or immersive technologies like Spherical Video-based Virtual Reality show promise in enhancing broader writing competencies, increasing student motivation, and fostering critical thinking. Nevertheless, issues such as interface complexity, potential inaccuracies in automated feedback, and overreliance on technology remain significant challenges. The limitations of this study include a narrow database search and an analysis conducted by authors of similar backgrounds, suggesting that future research should incorporate expanded data sources and collaborative revision to further validate and improve AES/AWE integration in EFL classrooms. In addition, future research should also investigate the accuracy of modern AWE or AES systems, which could be helpful for the development of other written production skills.

Keywords: Written Production, English as a Foreign Language, EFL, Artificial Intelligence, AI, Automatic Writing Evaluation, Automatic Essay Scoring

Introduction

In the last decades, the paradigm in language teaching has shifted from more traditional methods, such as the Grammar-Translation Method, towards approaches that prioritise the development of the communicative competence (Sullivan & Downey, 2015). In consequence, master classes, based on teacher-centered instruction, have been substituted by more “hands-on” classes, student-centered, wherein students are expected to make a direct use of the target language. However, teachers have reported problems in its implementation due to the high number of students in classes (Vijay & Suresh, 2023) and the teacher’s lack of time to develop materials for communicative teaching (Barasa & Omulando, 2014).

The latter could be related to the significant fraction of time teachers spend on tasks that are unrelated with direct in-class instruction and class preparation (McShane, 2022). Although teacher feedback is indispensable for the student’s growth in their language learning journey, Automatic Essay Scoring (AES) or Automatic Writing Evaluation (AWE) could provide more opportunities for practice without their depending on the teacher’s ability to correct them. However, little is known about whether the feedback provided by these systems can also support the student’s growth.

It is for this reason that this paper hopes to discover the effect of AES or AWS in the development of writing skills, as well as discovering the perceptions of both students and teachers on its implementation.

Objectives and methodology

AES or AWS tools have shown great potential in the development of written production. However, a detailed analysis of current literature is needed in order to comprehend the advantages and disadvantages it poses to the development of written production proficiency. This analysis is especially relevant due to the different methodologies that can be applied in the implementation of AES or AWE, and their effects on student growth.

It is for this reason that this article hopes to identify the main trends in the implementation of AES and AWE in English language classrooms, as well as the effect of these technologies on the development of written competence. It is worth noting that this paper does not only aim to merely report on current trends in research in this field,

but also to identify potential gaps and unexplored areas. To do so, four Research Questions (RQ) have been formulated.

1. What are the main ways in which AES and AWE are being integrated in language learning?
2. What effect do they have on the development of written production?
3. Are their effects dependent on the manner in which they are incorporated?
4. What are the main obstacles to their implementation in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms?

As a literature review, this paper follows a qualitative methodology. This is due to its focus being the identification of current trends in the implementation of AES and AWS through the analysis of current literature. Regarding the collection of such literature, two databases were searched: Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus. These databases were selected due to their high impact factor, as well as their rigour in the inclusion of articles.

In order to filter the most appropriate articles for this literature review, a search string was carefully crafted and adapted to each database. This search string included the relevant variations of both “Automatic Essay Scoring” and “English as a Foreign Language”, with the intention of achieving an exhaustive and representative collection of current literature in this area. However, it is worth noting that it only yielded a total of 23 articles among the two databases, of which 7 were selected. Figure 1 reflects the inclusion process.

Regarding the inclusion criteria, four conditions were set. First, only articles published between January 2020 and December 2024 have been included. This condition was set due to the rapid speed at which technology is evolving, which allows the possibility of the results of any previous study no longer being applicable to today’s classrooms, students or technology. The second condition is related to the type of data of each article, as only articles that deal with empirical data were considered. This decision is motivated by the desire to reach an objective and adequate conclusion about the research questions, for which empirical data is crucial. The third inclusion criteria is focused on the target language of the tools, as their training set can impact their performance on other languages than those it was created for. Lastly, the last inclusion condition deals with the focus of the research paper. Only those that focused on how the

implementation of AES or AWS tools affects the achievement of written production proficiency were selected for this review.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the selection process. Adapted from Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews.

Results

RQ1. What are the main ways in which AES and AWE are being integrated in language learning?

Two of the four articles are focused on conventional AWE systems, wherein an AWE system directly makes recommendations on the students' writing (Ajabshir & Ebadi, 2023; Hou, 2020). However, the objectives of their research vary. While Ajabshir and Ebadi

(2023) explore the effects the feedback from an AWE system, Grammarly, after a 15-weeks-long treatment, Hou (2020) studies the ability of Pigai, another AWE program, to increase the quality of students' writing after a single session. It is worth noting, however, that Ajabshir and Ebadi (2023) highlight the role of AWE as a support for teacher feedback, rather than a substitute to it.

Liu et al. (2023) compares the development of the writing production competence of students who used a Conventional AWE (C-AWE) approach to that of students who combined it with Peer Assessment (PA-AWE) after a 4-week-long period. In this context, a C-AWE approach may be described as those of Ajabshir and Ebadi (2023) and Hou (2020), wherein, independently of the duration of the treatment, an AWE system directly provides feedback to the students without any further interventions.

Lastly, Wang et al. (2022) acknowledge the shortcomings of traditional AWE systems regarding their evaluation of subjective factors, such as coherence, and investigates whether the combination of Spherical Video-based Virtual Reality (SVVR) with AWE systems might balance these shortcomings through its consequent processes of concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and evaluation and reflection. It is worth noting, however, that both SVVR and AWE systems are not used simultaneously in this approach. Instead, the AWE system is used as a way to solidify the information learnt through SVVR.

RQ2. What effect do they have on the development of written production?

Generally, the analysed literature points towards AWE systems exerting a good influence on the development of written production. Two of the studies on conventional AWE systems (Ajabshir & Ebadi, 2023; Hou, 2020) show that immediate, automated feedback is effective in reducing surface-level errors, which helps students improve their accuracy. The duration of the treatment also seems to play a crucial role, as Ajabshir and Ebadi (2023) found that a prolonged usage of Grammarly not only increased the linguistic accuracy of their students, but also influenced learners' willingness to revise their work.

However, systems such as Grammarly and Pigai focus mainly on accuracy and do not provide feedback on other relevant factors of written production. In contrast, approaches such as the PA-AWE (Liu et al., 2023) reveal that combining AWE with peer assessment leads to improvements beyond this simple error correction. More specifically,

students who participated in the PA-AWE experimental group tended to produce texts with a higher content organization, increased lexical diversity, and more coherent argumentation than those of the control (C-AWE) group. Additionally, the study carried out by Wang et al. (2022) suggests that the mental processes that take place through the combination of SVVR and AWE are capable of increasing the writing performance of students in the areas organization of content, originality, and elaboration, as well as helping achieve a greater learning achievement than students from the control group. In this study, the control group was constituted of students who used C-AWE systems.

RQ3. Are their effects dependent on the manner in which they are incorporated?

The analysed literature suggests the effectiveness of AWE systems, and, more specifically, AWE feedback, is highly dependent on the approach followed for its incorporation. For instance, while two of the articles suggest that applying conventional AWE systems as stand-alone tools yields improvements in the grammatical accuracy of the students (Ajabshir & Ebadi, 2023; Hou, 2020), the same cannot be said of other crucial factors of written production.

In contrast, when AWE is integrated with additional instructional strategies, such as peer assessment or immersive technologies, the benefits seem to extend to more global aspects of writing (Liu et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022). For instance, not only does the approach followed by Liu et al. (2023) seem to foster critical dialogue between the students regarding their own writing, but it also could help the students to become more aware of the kinds of error that are most common between their peers in order to avoid them in their own writing. In consequence, in addition to their writing proficiency, the experimental group also increased their motivation, critical thinking skills and reduced their writing anxiety. This idea is also supported by the SVVR–AWE approach proposed by Wang et al. (2022).

RQ4. What are the main obstacles to their implementation in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms?

Despite the promising outcomes associated with AWE systems, their implementation in EFL classrooms faces several challenges. A common obstacle noted across two studies is the narrow focus on grammatical accuracy of traditional AWE systems, which limits their usefulness to EFL learners (Liu et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022).

Moreover, as Ajabshir and Ebadi (2023) highlight, AWE systems may err in their evaluation. This is especially true for traditional systems, which focus on grammatical accuracy due to their potentially not understanding the contextual meaning of a word or sentence, thus categorising it as incorrect. Lastly, Liu et al. (2023) also mention the interface of the tools as an obstacle, as they might cause problems for students who are not familiar with them.

Discussion

This literature review highlighted the general trends in the implementation of AWS or AES systems in foreign language learning and teaching. The results indicate that traditional AWE systems, which focus mainly on the accuracy of the text, are still the most common AWE systems, although the approach to their implementation varies. In addition, the results suggest that the effects these approaches have in the development of the written competence of the students also differ. For instance, the C-AWE approach is only able to help improve the accuracy of students (Ajabshir & Ebadi, 2023; Hou, 2020), whereas other, more innovative approaches, such as PA-AWE and SVVR-AWE, can yield better results in the general development of this competence (Liu et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022).

Despite the fact that all analysed articles reported positive results after an AWE treatment, it is worth noting that the totality of the literature dealt only with traditional AWE systems, which are limited in the kind of feedback it can provide students with. Although new strategies have been tested in order to make up for these limitations with promising results, having the ability to limitlessly measure their own growth without depending on a teacher's or peer's ability to assess their production could help students in the self-regulation of their learning.

Furthermore, despite the good results of their study, Liu et al. (2023) mention that students relied on AWE and peer assessment only, as a teacher was not able to review peer assessment. In consequence, some students may doubt their peer's assessment and feel they have received an unjust grade (Hill & Edwards, 2019). These fears could not be irrational, as discrepancies between the judgement of teachers and students have been found in high complexity tasks (Tong et al., 2023). This shortcoming in PA-AWE approaches underscores the importance of researching the accuracy in the assessment

of new AWE and AES systems, which might be able to assess the coherence and fluidity of the text, as well as other relevant factors of the written competence.

Regarding the obstacles mentioned in the articles, the fallibility of AI systems, including AWE systems, highlight the importance of informing both teachers and students about their limitations to avoid an overreliance on technology. This idea is in line with that of Jie and Kamrozzaman (2024), who reported students tend to depend excessively on AI. Furthermore, the problems to understand the interface of the AI system, reported by Liu et al. (2023), are specially concerning. They bring to light the need to create user-friendly systems, so that even those who are not familiar with computers or programming languages are able to make use of this technology.

Conclusions

This literature review has provided insight into current trends regarding the implementation of AES or AWE systems in EFL classrooms. The findings reveal that traditional AWE systems, which focus mainly on grammatical accuracy, are still prevalent in language teaching. However, these systems also exhibit limitations, specially on their ability to foster broader skills within the written production competence (Liu et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022), such as content organization, coherence, or originality. In order to address these limitations, new instructional strategies have been developed, such as PA-AWE (Liu et al., 2023) and SVVR-AWE (Wang et al., 2022), which have shown promise in developing these broader skills.

Yet, some challenges still remain, including the narrow scope of traditional AWE systems (Liu et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022), possible inaccuracies in automated feedback (Ajabshir & Ebadi, 2023), and usability concerns related to interface complexity (Liu et al., 2023). These limitations highlight the importance of developing user-friendly interfaces for AWE systems, researching the accuracy in the assessment of new AWE or AES models and informing both teachers and students about the inherent limitations of these systems in order to prevent an overreliance on them.

Thus, despite the value of AES or AWE systems in supporting language teaching, their implementation must be approached carefully and thoughtfully from a methodological point of view in order to further foster the students' development of their written production competence. It must be noted, however, that this study is not without

limitations. First, only two databases were searched, which yielded a relatively low number of articles. This limited scope might not fully represent the entire spectrum of research on AES or AWE systems. Second, this literature review was carried out by authors of similar backgrounds, which limits the points of view from which the studies have been analysed. In consequence, the findings presented here might reflect unintentional biases or subjective interpretations.

Future research could address these limitations by including a broader range of databases and involving multiple authors from different backgrounds in the analysis process to enhance validity and reliability. Furthermore, exploring the application of modern AES or AWE systems, which could be able to assess subjective writing skills beyond grammatical accuracy, represents a valuable line of research for future investigations.

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